

Table 1. Selected peptides encoded by LncRNAs with oncogenic and oncosuppressor functions

Peptides sequence names	Peptide AA lenght	Cancers	Lnc-RNA symbols	Lnc-RNA name	Cellular compartment	Biological Function	Cell lines	References
<i>Micropeptides with oncogenic functions</i>								
CASIMO1	83	Breast cancer	SMIM22	small integral membrane protein 22	cytoplasm	Promotes cell proliferation and migration	MCF7, KPL1, T47D, MCF-10A,	[42]
LINC00511-133aa	133	Breast cancer	LINC00511	long intergenic non-protein coding RNA 511	nucleus	Regulates breast cancer cell invasion	MCF7, MDA-MB-231	[43]
UBAP1-AST6	117	Lung cancer	UBAP1 (MN_033243:1.1)	ubiquitin associated protein 1	nucleus	Promotes cell proliferation and colony formation	A549	[47]
SMIM30	59	Hepatocellular carcinoma	SMIM30	small integral membrane protein 30	cytoplasm, endoplasmic reticulum and mitochondria, membrane	Promotes tumour growth	SK-HEP-1	[50][51]
C20orf204-189AA	189	Hepatocellular carcinoma	C20orf204	chromosome 20 open reading frame 204	nucleus	Promotes cell proliferation	HeLa, Huh7, HepG2	[52]
Linc013026-68AA	68	Hepatocellular carcinoma	LINC013026		cytoplasm	promotes cell proliferation	HepG2, HeLa	[53]
JunBP	174	Hepatocellular carcinoma	LINC02551	long intergenic non-protein coding RNA 2551	cytoplasm	Promotes cell proliferation	97H, Hep3B	[54]
STMP1	47	Hepatocellular carcinoma	STMP1	short transmembrane mitochondrial protein 1	mitochondria	Promotes cell proliferation	Hepa1-6, Huh7, Sk-Hep-1	[55]
BVES-AS1-201-50aa	50	Colorectal cancer	BVES-AS1	BVES antisense RNA 1	nucleus	Promotes tumour cell viability, migration, and invasion in vitro	HCT116, SW480	[60]
SRSP	130	Colorectal cancer	FLJ20021	uncharacterized LOC90024	nucleus	Promotes tumorigenesis and progression	HCT-116, SW480, SW620	[61]
RBRP	71	Colon cancer	SEPTIN14P20	septin 14 pseudogene 20	nucleus	Promotes proliferation and metastasis	SW620, SW480	[62]
<i>Micropeptides with oncosuppressor functions</i>								
CIP2A-BP	52	Breast cancer	LINC00665	long intergenic non-protein coding RNA 665	cytoplasm	inhibited triple-negative breast cancer progression	MDA-MB-231, Hs578T, MCF-10A, BT549	[44]
ASRPS	60	Breast cancer	LINC00908	long intergenic non-protein coding RNA 908	cytoplasm	Inhibits triple-negative breast cancer angiogenesis	MDA-MB-231, Hs578T	[45]

EPR-encoded peptide (EPRp)	71	Breast cancer	<i>SMIM31</i>	small integral membrane protein 31	cytoplasm	Reduces breast cancer cell proliferation	NMuMG HEK-293	[46]
KRASIM	99	Hepatocellular carcinoma	<i>NCBP2-AS2</i>	NCBP2 antisense 2 (head to head)	cytoplasm	Inhibits oncogenic signals, cancer cell growth and proliferation	HuH-7, SK-HEP1	[56]
PINT87aa	87	Hepatocellular carcinoma	<i>LINC-PINT</i>	long intergenic non-protein coding RNA, p53 induced transcript	cytoplasm	Induces growth inhibition, cellular senescence, and decreases mitophagy	SMMC-7721, HepG2, HEK293	[57]
MPM	56	Hepatocellular carcinoma	<i>MTLN</i>	mitoregulin	mitochondria	Suppresses migration and invasion capabilities of hepatoma cells	Hepa1-6, SK-HEP1 SNU-449, HeLa	[58]
AC115619-22aa	22	Hepatocellular carcinoma	<i>AC115619</i>		nucleus	Inhibits growth and proliferation of cancer cells	PLC/PRF/5, HUH7	[59]
HOXB-AS3	53	Colorectal cancer	<i>HOXB-AS3</i>	HOXB cluster antisense RNA 3	nucleus	Inhibits growth of cancer cells	HTC-116	[20]
CRNDEP	84	Ovarian cancer and colorectal	<i>CRNDE</i>	colorectal neoplasia differentially expressed	nucleus	Regulates carcinogenesis and cell proliferation	HeLa	[63]
KDM4A-AS1	61	Esophageal squamous cell carcinoma	<i>KDM4A-AS1</i>	KDM4A antisense RNA 1	mitochondria membrane	Weakenes cancer cell viability and migratory capacity	KYSE150, TE-1	[64]
YY1BM	21	Esophageal squamous cell carcinoma	<i>LINC00278</i>	long intergenic non-protein coding RNA 278	cytoplasm	Regulates eEF2K expression and inhibits apoptosis	KYSE-30, Eca-109, TE-1	[65]
TLP18	18	Cervical cancer	<i>NKILA</i>	NF-kappaB interacting lncRNA	cytoplasm	Reduces cancer cell proliferation	SiHa, HeLa	[66]
MELOE-3	54	Melanoma	<i>MGC16025</i>	Uncharacterized LOC85009	nucleus	Improves T cell targets for immunotherapy	M113, M117	[69]
N1DARP	41	Pancreatic cancer	<i>LINC00261</i>	long intergenic non-protein coding RNA 261	cytoplasm	Tumor suppressor	Panc-1, Capan-1	[72]

LINC00665_18aa	18	Osteosarcoma	<i>LINC00665</i>	long intergenic non-protein coding RNA 665	nucleus	Suppresses viability, proliferation, and migration of human cells in vitro and diminishes tumour growth in vivo	<i>MNNG-HOS, U2OS OS</i>	[73]
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